

HERITALISE is an EU-funded project (2025-2028) that aims to revolutionise how we document and understand cultural heritage by advancing digitalisation and AI-powered tools. The project develops digitisation techniques to capture both visible and hidden features of heritage buildings and objects, using machine learning to transform raw data into valuable insights. HERITALISE integrates with the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH), providing a scalable, web-based platform for European cultural heritage institutions to share, access, and build on enriched digital resources for preservation and research.

- Full name: Heritage buildings and objects' digitisation & visualisation within the cloud
- Acronym: HERITALISE
- Number of partners: 17
- Start date: 1st January 2025
- Duration: 48 months
- EC funding: 4 196 368,71 €

Partners acronyms: IDP, University St. Andrews, Tekniker, Centro Conservazione Restauro La Venaria Reale, Fundación Santa María La Real, Politecnico di Torino, Comet Global Innovation, BDTA, Cyprus University of Technology, Open Geospatial Consortium, West Highland Museum, Timespan, Europeana, Heritage Malta, European Museum Academy, EIM

Welcome to the second issue of the HERITALISE Newsletter!

As we begin a new year, the HERITALISE project is proud to share the progress we have made in our mission to revolutionise the documentation and understanding of cultural heritage.

In recent months, we have reached important milestones, from our first General Assembly in the Scottish Highlands, several scientific publications, to showcasing our research at major international conferences.

We are committed to creating a new digital paradigm for cultural heritage, and we are thrilled to have you with us on this journey.

Thank you for your continued support as we work to bridge the past with the future.

PROJECT NEWS

Meet the People Powering HERITALISE

HERITALISE is powered by people as much as it is by technology. To highlight the human side of the project, we have launched a new video series, "Meet the Partners." This series will introduce you to the researchers, heritage professionals, technologists, and coordinators from across Europe who are working together to rethink how cultural heritage is documented, preserved, and shared.

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HERITALISE's First General Assembly in Helmsdale

The HERITALISE consortium held its first General Assembly from October 7-9, 2025, in the historic village of Helmsdale, Scotland. Hosted by the Timespan, the event brought together our partners from across Europe to refine project strategies, report on initial developments, and plan future actions. The assembly was a resounding success, fostering a strong sense of shared purpose and collaboration.

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HERITALISE Showcases Research at International Conferences

HERITALISE made a significant impact on the global stage, presenting its cutting-edge research at two of the world's most prestigious heritage science and technology events: the 30th CIPA International Symposium in Seoul and the Digital Heritage 2025 Congress in Siena. Our partners presented the project's vision for a holistic, interoperable digital ecosystem for cultural heritage, including the innovative "Memory Twin" concept.

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SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

HERITALISE. Project Insights and Initial Developments [▶ DOWNLOAD](#)

Integrated Survey for Heritage Digitisation – The Case Study of Venaria Reale [▶ DOWNLOAD](#)

Advanced digitisation and AI-powered data processing for Cultural Heritage: the HERITALISE Project [▶ DOWNLOAD](#)

Quality Certification in Data Acquisition for Cultural Heritage: The Power of Paradata for High Quality Digital 3D Cultural Heritage Assets [▶ DOWNLOAD](#)

From Digital Twin to Memory Twin: A Holistic Framework for Cultural Heritage Documentation, Interpretation, and Adaptive Reuse [▶ DOWNLOAD](#)

State-of-the-Art Review - Digitisation of Cultural Heritage: Methodologies, Technologies and Best Practices [▶ DOWNLOAD](#)

eCHOES

European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH)

The Cultural Heritage Cloud, or the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH), is a European Union initiative to create a shared digital infrastructure that connects cultural heritage institutions and professionals across the EU. It will provide digital collaboration tools, services, and data for the sector while facilitating access for smaller and more remote institutions.

This platform aims to add a digital dimension to heritage preservation, conservation, restoration, enhancement, and beyond by providing cutting-edge technology for tangible and intangible cultural heritage. HERITALISE is part of the ECCCH initiative, and we will make our tools available in the Cultural Heritage Cloud once this platform is set up.

The Cultural Heritage Cloud is being developed by ECHOES (European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science), a project funded by the European Commission and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

Interested to know more about ECHOES? Visit the [ECHOES website](#) for more information!

Or you can join the ECHOES Policy event, which will take place on February 5th, in Brussels, and the Second Annual Meeting, which will be held in Poznan, on March 18th.

EVENTS

EUROMED
International Conference on Digital Heritage
Cyprus University of Technology
Limassol, Cyprus
24th - 30th May 2026

EuroMed 2026, 24th -30th May 2026
Limassol, Cyprus

The 11th Euro-Mediterranean Conference on Digital Heritage (EuroMed 2026) will gather global experts to address the theme "Monuments, Memory and AI," focusing on the use of cutting-edge technologies for the protection, mass digitalization, and immersive presentation of cultural assets

[▶ MORE INFO](#)

BDTIC
6GH BUILDING DIGITAL TWIN
International Congress
June 01-04, 2026
Helsinki, Finland

BDTIC 2026, 26th -28th May 2026,
Brussels, Belgium

The 6th Building Digital Twin International Congress (BDTIC) will explore the role of "Digital Building Permits" and interoperable digital twins in decarbonizing the built environment, featuring collaborative sessions with European research initiatives focused on heritage site simulation.

[▶ MORE INFO](#)

ISPRS 2026
TORONTO
XXV ISPRS CONGRESS
FROM IMAGERY TO UNDERSTANDING
June 01-04, 2026
Helsinki, Finland

ISPRS 2026, 4th -11th July, Toronto, Canada

Under the theme, "From Imagery to Understanding," the XXV ISPRS Congress will explore the pivotal role of photogrammetry and remote sensing in creating intelligent 3D models and Digital Twins, highlighting how geospatial data and AI integration enhance the monitoring and conservation of global heritage sites.

[▶ MORE INFO](#)

135th MEMBER MEETING
Registration
Opens Soon!
JUNE 01-04, 2026
Helsinki, Finland

OGC Member Meeting 2025, 1st -4th June, Helsinki, Finland

The 135th OGC Member Meeting will focus on "Data Spaces and Interoperability," bringing together the global geospatial community to advance open standards for Digital Twins and secure data sharing, ensuring seamless integration between heritage documentation and broader urban geospatial infrastructures.

[▶ MORE INFO](#)

MEET THE PARTNERS

This video series highlights the people behind HERITALISE who are advancing innovation in digital heritage. Through short, easy-to-follow interviews, it presents a human perspective on the consortium, linking technical developments with the individuals who bring these ideas to life.

Mikel Borrás, IDP

Catherine Anne Cassidy, USTAN

Alberto Mendikute, TEKNIKER

Don't miss the videos, subscribe to our YouTube channel!

PRESENTATION VIDEO

WATCH THE VIDEO

We present our presentation video to you, which provides a compelling overview of our mission, the challenges we are facing, and how HERITALISE will impact society!!

SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTER

Be the first to learn about project events and activities!

JOIN US!